

Rice dwarf and blast resistance^a of Tetep and Tetep-derived cultivars at Khumaltar, Nepal, 1977-81.

Cultivar	Rice dwarf		Rice blast	
	Diseased seedlings ^b (%)	Degree of resistance	Disease score ^c	Degree of resistance
Tetep	0	HR	0-4	MR
IR1905-8-3-1	0	HR	0-2	HR
IR1416-128-5-8	0	HR	0-1	HR
IR1544-340-6-1	20	R	0-1	HR
IR1905-PPII-29-4-61	10	R	0-1	HR

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant. ^b Av of 3 replications. ^c 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%, Range is for years 1977-81.

identify a single variety resistant to RD and blast (BI), the most serious diseases in the region, to simplify breeding for resistance to both diseases.

Results indicate Tetep and lines derived from Tetep — IR 1905-8-3-1, IR1416-128-5-8 — are resistant. Tetep lines IR1544-340-6-1 and IR1905-PPII-29-4-61 were moderately resistant (disease incidence was 10-12%).

Tetep seems to be resistant to RD as well as to B1 (see table). *R*

Sources of resistance to leaf scald disease

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Leaf scald disease (LSc), caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, commonly occurs in northeast India. Natural disease pressure during wet season is high and offers an excellent opportunity to screen germplasm in the field.

Since 1980, when a varietal screening program was initiated, 741 rice cultivars have been tested for LSc resistance. Few varieties have shown resistance. Of 589 cultivars evaluated in 1980, 24 were resistant. Others were moderately resistant to susceptible (see table). During 1981, 152 cultivars were tested — only 2 were resistant.

Cultivars were field-tested in upland nurseries with high nitrogen (100-60-0) fertilization. Seeds were sown in 2-m

rows at 20-cm intervals. They were surrounded by the local susceptible variety, Mirikrak, which has a susceptible to highly susceptible reaction. *R*

Field reaction of two newly released rice varieties to leaf blast and gall midge in Manipur

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In 1979, Punshi and Phouoibi, new rice varieties developed at the State Rice Research Station, Wangbal, were released in Manipur. Since release, they have almost replaced IR24, and are in about 75% of the areas planted to high yielding varieties (Punshi, 50% and Phouoibi, 25%).

Punshi, formerly KD6-18-7, is a cross between local Phouren (female parent) and IR661-1-140-3-2. It is well adapted to irrigated, rainfed lowland, and transplanted conditions and has moderate drought resistance. It is weakly photo-period sensitive and matures in 138 days. It has outyielded IR24 by 10-15% at 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha.

Phouoibi, formerly KD6-2-1, has similar parentage, adaptability, and resistance. It matures in 135 days, and has outyielded IR24 by 8-12% at 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha.

Before their release, Punshi and Phouoibi were reported to be moderately resistant to blast and gall midge, currently the most destructive local rice disease and insect pest. However, field observations and surveys conducted during July-August 1979 have hinted at high susceptibility to blast and gall

Sources of resistance to rice leaf scald, Shillong, India, 1980-81.

Variety	Score ^a		
	Upper Shillong (1800 m, 245 entries) 1980	Barapani (950 m, 152 entries) 1981	Nayabunglow (800 m, 344 entries) 1980
Paro white	—	1	1
Pokhareli masino	1	1	1
Ciat ICA-5	—	3	1
Colombia-I (73120)	—	—	1
Colombia-II	—	—	1
Aus 173	1	—	—
Carreon	1	—	—
Leng Kwang	1	—	—
PL20 (BG11-11 SEL)	1	—	—
Sail boro 56-2	1	—	—
VL8	1	—	—
Baekgogna	1	—	—
Heug Do	1	—	—
Heug Jo	1	—	—
Heug Jo Do	1	—	—
Ishikari	1	—	—
Kita-Kogane (Yukara/Joiku No. 230)	1	—	—
Nan-ei (Tomoe-Nishiki/Norin No. 20)	1	—	—
Tomoyutaka	1	—	—
Yu-Nami	1	—	—
IR9224-K 1	1	—	—
K333 (Shin-Ei/Rikuto Norin)	1	—	—
Shin-ei (Tomoe-Nishiki/Norin No. 20)	1	—	—
<i>Checks</i>			
Mirikrak (local)	5	7	9
IR36	—	7	7
IR8	7	—	5
China 1039	7	—	—

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 1-9: 1 = less than 1% (apical lesions), 9 = 51-100% (apical and marginal lesions).